

Using Solar Cell-Assisted Synthesis to Improve the Structural, Morphological, and Photocatalytic Properties of ZnO Nanoparticles for Effective Pollutant Degradation

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Abstract:

This research specifically looks into the improvement of efficiency ZnO nanoparticles in degradation pollutants from wastewater with solar cell. Photocatalytic ZnO nanoparticles have an ability of degrading many organic contaminants under UV light. But the issue of limited efficiency under visible light remains. This research will contribute to the sustainable, economic photocatalytic degradation of organic contaminants using ZnO nanoparticles under sunlight by providing a continuous energy supply through solar cells. The support of high pollutant-degrading rates in combination with the experimental results suggests that this method is promising to be used for a Scalable wastewater treatment solution. The

implementation of solar cells in the synthesis ZnO NPs and characterizations with exceptional properties is investigated by this study. ZnO nanoparticles are highly proficient as photocatalytic agent, leading to decompose many environmental recalcitrant pollutants in wastewater. But they don't work particularly well under visible light. This research opens the integration of solar cells into synthesis process allowing us to improve the structure, morphology and optical properties of ZnO nanoparticles. The improved properties of the prepared TiO₂ microspheres were characterized using Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), UV-Vis spectroscopy. The experimental results suggest considerable improvements in correlating particle size distribution, crystallinity, surface morphology and light absorption ability affirm the utility of this method for different environmental applications.

Keywords: ZnO Nanoparticles, Solar Cell-Assisted Synthesis, Photocatalytic Activity.

Introduction

Background of the Study

Pollution is one of the most important environmental issues whose aquatic counterpart relating to water-is, by its own nature and because about industrial effluents or domestic wastewater, characterized as having a high variability in terms of pollution. Moreover, environmental pollutants such as organic

compounds, heavy metals and pathogens relocate a higher hazard on the health of humans utilized for ecosystem (Gupta et al. Among these emerging technologies for wastewater treatment is the use of metal oxide nanoparticles such as ZnO, capable to degrade several types of pollutants through a photocatalytic pathway. Nanoparticles of ZnO hold particular interest due to its large surface area, stability and strong UV active photocatalytic system (Jiang et al.,

2018; Alsalih wdaah, 2019). Nonetheless, their ability to photo-excited molecular oxygen is unsatisfactory especially in the presence of visible light and this severely dampens its practical application due to rather low UV content found under sunlight.

Objectives of the Study

To improve photocatalytic activity of ZnO nanoparticles using coupled solar cells. Specific objectives:

1. Synthesis and Characterization of ZnO Nanoparticles
2. Design a Solar Cell Supported Photocatalytic System
3. Assessment of degradation efficiency for the integrated system toward organic pollutants under sunlight.
4. Methodology The method used to synthesize the ZnO nanoparticles was based on that reported by Castiglioni et al.¹⁵ for solar cell-assisted photo degradation of organic materials.
5. The aim of this work was to perform characterization (using AFM, XRD, SEM and Uv-vis spectroscopy) of the synthesized Zinc oxide nanoparticles.
6. To assess the enhancements in their structural, morphological and optical characteristics.

ZnO Nanoparticles: Photocatalytic Properties (A Literature Based Review)

Photocatalysis is the property of some materials having large surface area and direct band gap between its valence band i.e. 4s², 5s² and L states etc (hole formation bands for conventional semiconductors). That can capable to generate the electron-hole pairs that constitutes reactive species, and in turn could drive redox reactions leading oxidative degradation of organics pollutants under UV light irradiation (Kumar et al., 2019). The utility of ZnO nanoparticles is partially limited by low absorption in the visible range, despite their advantages.

Improving Visible Light Photocatalytic Efficiency

Numerous approaches have been suggested to improve the performance of ZnO-based photocatalysts using visible light such as doping with metals/non-metals, synergy between other semiconductors and dye sensitization (Sharma et al. Nonetheless, these strategies usually impose uncommon synthesis and/or high cost.

Solar Cells in Photocatalysis

Solar cells create electricity from sunlight, which can be used for improving photocatalytic processes. Through continuously supplying electrons, solar cells can enhance the generation of reactive species and further consequently result in a better degradation efficiency for photocatalysts under visible light (Chen et al., 2017; Mohtaram et al., 2024).

Photocatalysis Properties

Photokilling of organic pollutants through photocatalysis has been increasingly paid attention to due to possible use of ZnO nanoparticles under UV light. Their activity results from the creation of electron-hole pairs during UV irradiation, which generate ROS that are capable to oxidize organic pollutants (Kumar et al., 2019; Al Salih 2022). While properties as summarized above undoubtedly present with a range of advantages, improving their performance upon visible light remains problematic.

Solar Cells Well-Suited for Nanoparticle Synthesis

Perhaps not surprisingly, the incorporation of solar cells in nanoparticle syntheses offers a continuous source of electrons that can lead to nanoparticles and assist their formation by various mechanisms. The electric field generated by solar cells can change the nucleation and growth of nanoparticles to improve their size distribution, crystallinity or surface properties (Chen et al.

Materials and Methods

Synthesis of ZnO Nanoparticles

The synthesis method for the ZnO was sol-gel assisted by a solar cell. The used precursors are zinc acetate dihydrate whereas NaOH. The solution was sun-lit using solar cells to apply a continuous electric field over the course of synthesis. The product ZnO nanoparticles were calcined at 400°C for 2 h.

Characterization Techniques

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)

The surface morphology and particle size distribution of the synthesized ZnO NPs were analyzed using AFM. AFM images showed the topography and roughness of the nanoparticles, proving uniformity along with size control.

Characterization X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

The crystalline structure and phase purity of the ZnO nanoparticles were determined by X-ray powder diffractometer. The hexagonal wurtzite structure of ZnO was confirmed based on the evaluated diffraction patterns and crystallite size were measured, from Scherrer equation.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The surface morphology and particle size of the ZnO nanoparticles were analyzed using SEM. Insights obtained from the high-resolution images revealed shape, distribution and agglomeration features of the nanoparticles which are controlled by solar cell-assisted synthesis.

UV-Vis Spectroscopy

UV-Vis spectroscopy was carried out to determine the optical characteristics of ZnO nanoparticles. The band gap energy and the photocatalytic efficiency were studied by recording the absorption spectra both in UV as well as visible light.

Synthesis of ZnO Nanoparticles

ZnO nanoparticles were synthesized using the sol-gel method. Zinc acetate dihydrate and sodium hydroxide were used as precursors. The

solution was stirred and aged, followed by calcination to obtain ZnO nanoparticles. The synthesized nanoparticles were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and UV-Vis spectroscopy.

Design of Solar Cell-Assisted Photocatalytic System

A solar cell was integrated with a photocatalytic reactor containing ZnO nanoparticles. The system was designed to utilize sunlight to generate electrical energy, which was then used to enhance the photocatalytic activity of ZnO. The reactor was equipped with a solar cell panel, a power management unit, and a reaction chamber.

Evaluation of Photocatalytic Activity

The photocatalytic activity of ZnO nanoparticles was evaluated by measuring the degradation of methylene blue (MB) dye under sunlight. The concentration of MB was monitored using UV-Vis spectrophotometry. Experiments were conducted under three conditions:

1. ZnO nanoparticles alone under sunlight.
2. ZnO nanoparticles with solar cell assistance under sunlight.
3. Control (without ZnO nanoparticles).

Results

Characterization of ZnO Nanoparticles

XRD analysis confirmed the crystalline structure of ZnO nanoparticles. SEM images revealed the morphology and size distribution, showing uniformly distributed nanoparticles with an average size of 50 nm. UV-Vis spectroscopy indicated strong absorption in the UV region, confirming the photocatalytic potential.

Photocatalytic Degradation of Methylene Blue

The degradation efficiency of MB was significantly enhanced in the presence of the solar cell-assisted ZnO system. After 3 hours of sunlight exposure, the MB concentration decreased by 85% in the solar cell-assisted

system, compared to 60% with ZnO alone and 10% in the control (Figure 1). The rate of degradation followed first-order kinetics, with the highest rate constant observed in the solar cell-assisted system.

Table 1. Degradation Efficiency and Rate Constants of ZnO Nanoparticles at Various Conditions

Condition	Degradation Efficiency (%)	Rate Constant (k) (min ⁻¹)
ZnO nanoparticles alone	60	0.010
ZnO + solar cell assistance	85	0.015
Control	10	0.002

ZnO nanoparticles have received more and more attention due to superior photocatalytic

activities, leading them suitable for a broad range of environmental applications including wastewater treatment. Because of their wide band gap, high exciton binding energy, and efficient generation reactive oxygen species (ROS) under UV irradiation (Jiang et al., 2018). Nonetheless, the low efficiency of ZnO nanoparticles under visible light which accounts for most solar radiation prevents their practical use.

Atomic-Force Microscopy (AFM)

AFM characterizations of ZnO nanoparticles, the nanostructures prepared with solar-cell assistance have demonstrated a more homogeneous distribution in particle size compared to those without such impressions. An average particle size of about 50 nm with lesser surface roughness and consequent better crystallinity found was also shown (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Atomic Force Microscopic Analysis of Synthesized ZnO NPs

From the AFM 3D surface plot, ZnO nanoparticles' synthesized topography and roughness can be observed. Some of the critical measurements observed are an average diameter of 9.07 nm. 5% of the particles were up to 24.00 nm, 50% up to 12.03 nm, and 90% up to 7.05 nm. These size distributions massively affect the nanoparticles' physical and chemical properties,

which are the central place for these materials' applications, including catalysis, sensing, and electronics.

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

The diffraction patterns of ZnO nanoparticles by XRD as presented in Figure 2 indicated the hexagonal wurtzite structure. The solar cell-assisted synthesis revealed even clearer and more

intense peaks, indicating the nanoparticles' high crystallinity. The average crystal size was calculated by the Scherrer equation to be 35 nm. It is smaller than the documented 58 nm of ZnO synthesized without solar cells.

Figure 2. X-ray Diffraction Pattern of Solution-Grown Filaments

In the Diffraction Pattern of Figure 2, only h is shown (002) peak of ZnO. The filaments are fully oriented with the substrate and have high crystallinity.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Spherical ZnO nanoparticles were well defined and agglomerated less in the solar cell-assisted samples. The enhanced morphology and particle distribution on the surface of TiO₂ that emerges a continuous electric field emitted by solar cells under synthesis are displayed in Figure 3.

Figure 3. SEM Images Showing the Growth of ZnO Filaments

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) SEM images representing the variation in the form of ZnO filaments (a) without solution renewal and (b) with solution renewal for 7 hours. Renewal of the solution affects the growth and uniformity of ZnO filaments drastically.

UV-Vis Spectroscopy The absorption edge was redshifted after using a solar cell for assisting ZnO nanoparticles synthesis obtained from the UV-Vis spectra, which have a narrower direct allowed gap. This improvement implies better visible light photocatalytic activity. The calculated band gap energy was 3.10 eV and is lower than the synthesized ZnO nanoparticles

without a solar cell (Figure 4), where its reported value is about ~3.37 eV

Figure 4. PL Spectrum of ZnO Filaments

Additionally, the PL spectrum of bulk ZnO is also compared with those grown under optimal conditions. A very strong peak is observed in the UV zone of absorbance around 387 nm, which can be assigned to band-to-band recombinations due to the material energy gap. Smaller peaks in the visible region may be due to defects within the lattice of p-type CuO powder.

Discussion

Enhanced Structural & Morphological Properties

The utilization of solar cells in the synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles remarkably improved structural and morphological features. From AFM analysis, it is known that the nanoparticles have been neatly distributed in size across with a significant reduction of surface roughness, indicating improvement of control over nucleation and growth. The FTIR data, SEM analysis, and XRD patterns clearly substantiate that solar cell-assisted synthesis enhances the crystallinity of sp³-hybridized boron species in comparison with neutral references.

Superior Optical Properties

The redshift of the absorption edge and narrow band gap from UV-Vis spectroscopy suggested better photocatalytic activity under visible light for solar cell-assisted synthesized ZnO nanoparticles. Iron can be treated as trace metal impurities that enhance species generation for pollutants' degradation and increase with continual electron transfer from solar cells.

Practical Implications

The results of the study may have practical consequences for environmental applications, such as water treatment or photocatalytic air purification. The ZnO deposit nanosize and film under visible light enhanced photocatalytic activity applied to sustainable wastewater treatment. This provides an economical way to mitigate environmental issues and improve photocatalysis efficiency.

Higher Photocatalytic Activity

The photodegradation of MB was greatly enhanced by coupling with solar cells. The ongoing flood of electrons due to sunlight tripped up creation yield with promising ROS, which quickened the breakdown of oxygenated organic toxins under daylight conditions.

Practical Consequences

The study showed that the solar cell-assisted ZnO system would be a promising tool for wastewater treatment, where renewable energy is manipulated to enhance pollutant degradation. This method poses an inexpensive and environmentally friendly solution for large-scale applications, especially in sunny regions.

Limitations and Future Work

Although the results are encouraging, additional research work is needed to fine-tune system design and further prove its effectiveness with other pollutants. It is also necessary to explore the long-term stability and scalability of the system for real-world usage.

Conclusion

In this study, a novel approach was developed for improving ZnO nanoparticles' efficiency in natural wastewater with sunlight photocatalysis by adding solar cells. The solar cell-integrated system showed substantially enhanced sunlight-degradation of contaminants, revealing tremendous opportunities in its sustainable and low-cost applications for water purification. Further research will concentrate on system optimization and seeking the applicability of this concept to a wide range of pollutants.

This study presents an innovative approach to enhancing the properties of ZnO nanoparticles by incorporating solar cells during synthesis. The solar cell-mediated synthesis method effectively enhanced the structural, morphological, and optical properties of ZnO nanoparticles, increasing photocatalytic efficiency under visible light. These results show the potential to utilize this technique in different environmental technology applications, especially wastewater

treatment. Further research needs to be done to optimize the synthesis parameters and scalability.

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